

1 **Maternal exercise rescues fetal akinesia-impaired joint and bone development**

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37 **Abstract**

38 Fetal movements exert mechanical forces that shape the developing skeleton. Conditions that impair fetal
39 movement can cause skeletal defects, but interventions are limited. Here, we show that maternal wheel
40 running exercise regulates fetal skeletal development in mice. In wild-type fetuses, maternal exercise
41 stimulated joint morphogenesis and bone development. These changes could not be fully explained by
42 altered placental transport. Therefore, we next evaluated the effects of maternal exercise in the Splotch-
43 delayed (Sp^d) mouse model of fetal akinesia, which features intact maternofetal communication, but
44 homozygous mutants lack contractile skeletal muscle. Maternal exercise substantially rescued fetal akinesia-
45 impaired joint and bone development and prevented disuse-induced resorption of the deltoid tuberosity.
46 Further, bioreactor mechanical stimulation of explanted Sp^d limbs, which remove systemic factors, similarly
47 stimulated joint morphogenesis. Together, these findings identify maternal exercise as a regulator of fetal
48 skeletal development, provide a platform for studying skeletal developmental mechanobiology and suggest
49 potential therapeutic implications for maternal exercise in skeletal conditions caused by impaired fetal
50 movement.

51

52 **Keywords:**

53 Maternal exercise, Splotch-delayed mice, Fetal akinesia, Bone, Joints, Development, Mechanobiology,
54 Placenta, Bioreactor

55 1.0 Introduction

56 Spontaneous fetal movements exert mechanical forces that shape the developing skeleton. The first fetal
57 movements begin with the initiation of muscle formation and coincide with joint and bone development.^{1,2}
58 Reduced fetal movements (*i.e.*, fetal hypokinesia) can cause congenital defects in skeletal development,
59 including hip dysplasia, congenital scoliosis, joint contractures, and delayed bone formation.^{3,4} Etiologically,
60 fetal hypokinesia-associated syndromes exist on a broad phenotypic spectrum from mild to perinatal lethal,
61 with fetal akinesia (*i.e.*, no movements) being the most severe.⁵ Fetal hypokinesia can be associated with
62 intrauterine environmental conditions, such as breech fetal position^{6,7} and insufficient amniotic fluid (*i.e.*,
63 oligohydramnios),⁸ genetic mutations that affect neuromuscular development (e.g., genetic forms of
64 arthrogryposis),⁹ or non-genetic conditions with abnormal movements *in utero* (e.g., amyoplasia).^{10,11} While
65 fetal hypokinesia-causing conditions can sometimes be detected by prenatal imaging and/or genetic
66 screening, treatment of skeletal abnormalities is currently limited to postnatal interventions, including
67 surgeries, bracing, and physical therapy.¹²⁻¹⁷ This treatment gap stems both from limited mechanistic
68 understanding of how fetal movements direct skeletal development and limited means for prenatal
69 intervention. Here, using mouse models, we demonstrate that maternal exercise during fetal gestation can
70 alter fetal joint and bone morphogenesis and can substantially rescue both joint and bone formation in a
71 preclinical model of fetal akinesia.

72
73 Animal models of limited fetal movement recapitulate the skeletal defects observed in fetal akinesia patients.
74 Early experiments used transplanted embryonic chick limb buds, which lack innervation, to infer that disrupted
75 muscle development causes defects in joint cavitation and shape and bone formation.^{18,19} Subsequent studies
76 used pharmacological agents and motor neuron resection to paralyze chick embryos, and observed similar
77 defects in both joint and long bone development.²⁰⁻²⁸ Mouse models of fetal akinesia have further enabled
78 mechanistic insights into how muscle contractions guide mammalian skeletal development. The muscular
79 dysgenesis (*mdg/mdg*) and Splotch-delayed (*Sp^d*) mouse models are products of spontaneous mutations.
80 *Mdg/mdg* mice harbor a mutation in the DHPaR1 receptor that prevents excitation-contraction coupling²⁹⁻³¹
81 and *Sp^d* mice feature a point mutation at the Pax3 gene that abrogates muscle progenitor cell migration
82 and limits skeletal muscle development.³²⁻³⁴ Additional models have been genetically engineered to disrupt
83 fetal muscle development, including the *Myf5^{-/-}:MyoD^{-/-}* amyogenic mouse, which lacks striated muscle due
84 to deletion of the myogenic regulatory factors *Myf5* and *MyoD*.³⁵ Skeletal development studies using these
85 models consistently show that *in utero* muscle function is required for proper fetal joint morphogenesis and
86 bone formation.³⁶⁻⁴³ Additionally, fetal muscle contraction regulates the growth and maturation of bony
87 eminences at tendon insertion sites, such as the deltoid tuberosity of the humerus, which initiates via a
88 cartilaginous rudiment that resorbs in the absence of fetal movements.⁴⁴ The coherence of these findings
89 across human patients and animal models implicates the loss of muscle-generated mechanical forces in fetal
90 akinesia-associated defects in skeletal development.

91
92 *Ex vivo* bioreactor cultures complement *in vivo* animal models of fetal akinesia by allowing the application
93 of mechanical stimulation during fetal skeletal development.^{45–48} Previously, using bioreactor culture of
94 embryonic chick limb explants, we showed that the amplitude, frequency, and duration of joint flexion
95 regulate joint morphogenesis *ex vivo*.^{49,50} We further used mouse limb explant culture to demonstrate the
96 roles of specific molecular mechanosensors and mechanotransducers in the mechanoregulation of skeletal
97 morphogenesis. Using pharmacologic inhibition and conditional genetic ablation approaches, we showed
98 that the mechanosensitive ion channel, Transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V member 4
99 (TRPV4), mediates joint morphogenesis in response to applied limb movement,^{51,52} and the
100 mechanoresponsive transcriptional regulators, Yes-associated protein (YAP) and Transcriptional co-activator
101 with PDZ-binding motif (TAZ), mediate load-induced fetal bone formation.⁵³ Developmentally, we found that
102 YAP/TAZ mechanosignaling in vessel-associated osteoblast precursor cells coordinates blood vessel invasion
103 and growth plate remodeling at the chondro-osseous junction during fetal bone development.⁵³ These
104 findings suggest that both cartilaginous joint morphogenesis and endochondral ossification are mechanically
105 regulated. In the context of fetal akinesia, we found that *ex utero* dynamic mechanical stimulation rescues
106 collagen extracellular matrix deposition and organization in *Sp^d* mice.⁵⁴ These bioreactor studies have
107 enabled interrogation of the molecular basis by which absent and restored mechanical signals regulate
108 skeletal morphogenesis, but are limited by extraction from the fetal vascular system and from systemic
109 factors provided by the gestational environment. Thus, explants can only be cultured for a limited duration
110 in an environment that cannot perfectly mimic *in utero* conditions.

111
112 In addition to active movements exerted by the fetus, passive movements imparted on the fetal skeleton by
113 maternal activity may also guide development. Motivated by the observation that *Sp^d* and *mdg/mdg* mice
114 exhibit greater defects in the forelimb than hindlimb,^{55–57} we reasoned that passive mechanical stimuli from
115 maternal movements may produce distinct mechanical environments in forelimbs and hindlimbs. By applying
116 displacement boundary conditions, such as could be brought about by maternal activity, to finite element
117 models of the forelimb and hindlimb, we observed greater stresses and strains in the developing femur
118 compared to the humerus.⁵⁸ This is plausible since in the developing fetus, the shape and mostly planar
119 alignment of the forelimb positions the elbow joint closer to the central axis of the fetus. The hindlimb knee
120 joint is angled away from the body, potentially increasing the lever arm effect of loads applied externally
121 to the limb. Thus, passive movements on the fetus may impart greater stresses and strains on fetal hindlimbs
122 than forelimbs, which correlates with the *in vivo* findings that *Sp^d* mice show less severe defects in knee
123 morphogenesis than elbow and shoulder.^{55–57} Based on this reasoning, we hypothesized that passive fetal
124 movements induced by maternal exercise could provide formative mechanical signals to the developing
125 fetus. Here, we test this hypothesis through application of maternal exercise in wild-type and *Sp^d* mice, with
126 a focus on morphogenesis of the humerus.

127

128 Current guidelines recommend maternal exercise for healthy pregnancies. Regular moderate-intensity
129 exercise during pregnancy reduces maternal risk of gestational disorders (e.g., gestational diabetes,
130 gestational hypertension),⁵⁹⁻⁶¹ enhances birth outcomes (e.g., reduced preterm birth rate, increased vaginal
131 birth rate),⁶²⁻⁶⁴ and improves offspring health (e.g., cardiac function, cerebral maturation).^{65,66} Though clinical
132 evidence suggests multifaceted benefits of maternal exercise, we do not fully understand how maternal
133 exercise affects fetal development. Maternal blood and fetal blood are separated by the placenta; thus,
134 all nutrients needed by the fetus are transported across the placenta. Prior studies suggest that maternal
135 exercise may increase nutrient transport to the developing fetus via the placenta and/or upregulate specific
136 humoral signaling molecules that are transferred to the developing fetus (e.g., insulin-like growth factor 1
137 (IGF-1)).⁶⁷⁻⁶⁹ Common metrics used to assess placental transport efficiency include the fetal weight to
138 placental weight ratio (FW:PW), placental histomorphometry, and nutrient transporter expression.⁷⁰
139 Currently, experimental evidence is limited in understanding how maternal exercise affects fetal skeletal
140 development and continued research is required.

141

142 Here, we show that maternal exercise regulates fetal skeletal development in mice. We find that maternal
143 exercise stimulates joint morphogenesis, deltoid tuberosity formation, and bone growth in wild-type fetuses
144 and largely rescues fetal akinesia-impaired skeletal abnormalities in *Sp^d* mice. Our data suggest that these
145 benefits are mediated by passive movements imparted on the developing skeleton by maternal exercise,
146 but do not rule out contributions from altered maternofetal signaling. These findings identify maternal
147 exercise as a regulator of fetal skeletal development, implicate maternal exercise as a putative platform
148 for studying skeletal developmental mechanobiology *in vivo*, and motivate further investigation of maternal
149 exercise as a potential *in utero* intervention for fetal hypokinesia-associated skeletal syndromes.

150 **2.0 Materials and methods**

151

152 **2.1 Animal husbandry and care**

153 C57BL/6J male and female mice were purchased from the Jackson Laboratory (Jackson Laboratory, Bar
154 Harbor, ME, USA). Mice were housed and bred for experiments at the University of Pennsylvania.
155 Heterozygous Splotch-delayed ($Pax3^{sp^d/+}$) male and female mice were also purchased from the Jackson
156 Laboratory. These mice were housed and bred at Imperial College London. Sp^d embryos were genotyped
157 using PCR on DNA derived from embryonic head tissue. DNA underwent 30 30 second reaction cycles at
158 94°C, 60°C, and 74°C. For controls, the following primers were used: 5' AGGGCCGAGTCAACCAGCACG
159 3' and 3' CACGCGAAGCTGGCGAGAAATG 5'. For mutants, the following primers were used: 5'
160 AGTGTCCACCCCTCTTGGCCTCGGCCGAGTCAACCAGGTCC 3' and 3'
161 CACGCGAAGCTGGCGAGAAATG 5'

162

163 Prior to maternal exercise experiments, all mice were fed regular chow (Purina LabDiet, St. Louis, MO, USA)
164 *ad libitum* and housed in cages containing 2–4 animals each. Mice were maintained at constant 25°C on a
165 12 hr light/dark cycle. Protocols were approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committees at the
166 University of Pennsylvania for experiments conducted in the United States (Protocol no: 806482) and United
167 Kingdom experiments were conducted under the UK Home Office Project License number PPL P39D18B9C.
168 All US-based animal procedures were performed in adherence to United States federal guidelines of animal
169 care. All UK-based procedures were performed in accordance with the UK Animals Scientific Procedures Act
170 of 1986 and were approved by the institutional Animal Welfare and Ethical Review Body (AWERB).
171 Additionally, experiments were conducted in accordance with the 3R principles in animal research.^{71–73}

172

173 **2.2 Maternal exercise**

174 Virgin female C57BL/6J mice were housed individually with the Mouse Home Cage Running Wheel system
175 (Columbus Instruments, Columbus, OH) for at least two weeks prior to timed matings. This free-spinning wheel
176 running system allowed us to measure voluntary running activity during the acclimation period. After timed
177 pregnancies, mice were individually housed, without running wheels, from E0 to E13.5. Mated females were
178 weighed at E0 and E12.5 to confirm pregnancy by weight gain. For *ad libitum* wheel running experiments,
179 dams pregnant with E13.5 embryos were re-housed with their running wheels and allowed to run freely from
180 E13.5 through E17.5, with harvest at E17.5. For supervised wheel running experiments, mice were individually
181 housed without running wheels from E13.5 through E17.5, but exercised daily from E13.5 to E16.5, inclusive
182 (**Figure S1A**). Each day, the pregnant dam was transferred back to her cage with the running wheel and
183 placed onto the wheel. To prevent encourage running, the wheel was lifted slightly off the ground for each
184 bout of exercise. Mice exercised for 15 min, then rested for 15 min with the wheel back in the cage. This
185 process was repeated four times, so that dams received 1 hr of encouraged wheel running exercise, per

186 day. At the end of this exercise regimen, pregnant dams were returned to their cages without wheels. Sham
187 mice were included in *ad libitum* and supervised wheel running experiments, which received the same access
188 to wheels, but the wheels were locked to prevent running.

189
190 Humane endpoints were predefined, including criteria such as poor grooming, sunken eyes, hunched posture,
191 severe axial deviation, lack of food and water intake, significant weight loss, bloody feces, severe
192 respiratory issues, debilitating diarrhea, seizures, paresis, and abscesses. No adverse effects of exercise
193 were observed in any of the mice and no humane endpoints were reached during the study. Pregnant dams
194 were monitored closely until euthanasia, when embryos reached E17.5.

195
196 *Ad libitum* wheel access during the maternal exercise period yielded highly variable running distances and
197 low running distances at later timepoints that are important for joint and bone development (**Figure S1B-D**).
198 Thus, Sp^d mice were only exercised using supervised wheel running. Sp^d mice underwent the same procedures
199 described above, except embryos were harvested at E16.5.

200

201 **2.3 Microcomputed tomography (μCT)**

202 The Microct45 system (SCANCO Medical Ag, Brüttisellen, Switzerland) was used to capture high-resolution
203 three-dimensional (3D) microcomputed tomography (MicroCT) images of fixed E17.5 forelimbs from
204 C57BL/6J embryos. E17.5 forelimbs were submerged in phosphate buffered saline (PBS, Thermo Fisher
205 Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) for image capture. The following imaging parameters were applied: isotropic
206 voxel size of 3 μm, integration time of 300 ms, x-ray intensity of 114 μA, and peak tube voltage of 70
207 kVp. A three-dimensional Gaussian filter of 1.2 with filter support of 2 was used for noise suppression, and
208 mineralized tissue was segmented from the PBS or soft tissue using a threshold of 140 mgHA/cm³. The
209 acquired images were analyzed using the manufacturer-provided software.

210

211 **2.4 Optical projection tomography (OPT)**

212 Right forelimbs from E17.5 C57BL/6J embryos and E16.5 Sp^d embryos were harvested for skeletal
213 preparations with Alcian blue (MilliporeSigma, Billerica, MA, USA) and Alizarin red (MilliporeSigma).⁷⁴
214 Harvested forelimbs were frozen at -20°C prior to preparation. Upon thawing, samples were dissected to
215 remove the outer epidermal layer, which improves stain penetration, then incubated in 95% (v/v) ethanol
216 (Decon Laboratories Inc., Swedeland, PA, USA) overnight. The next day, samples were washed with acetone
217 (MilliporeSigma) for 1-2 hr, then incubated with acetone overnight. After acetone incubation, samples were
218 rinsed with deionized water (ddH₂O) for 1-2 hr, then incubated for 24 hr in a 150 mg/L Alcian blue solution
219 (80% ethanol (v/v), 20% acetic acid (v/v) (Thermo Fisher Scientific)). The following day, samples were
220 washed with 70% ethanol (v/v) four times for 1 hr each, washed for 1 hr with 1% potassium hydroxide
221 (KOH, w/v) (VWR International, Radnor, PA, USA), then incubated overnight in a 50 mg/L Alizarin red

222 solution (1% KOH (w/v), ddH₂O). After Alizarin red incubation, the stain was gently poured off and samples
223 were placed in a storage mixture (50% ethanol (v/v), 50% glycerol (v/v) (MilliporeSigma) and stored at
224 4°C until embedding for optical projection tomography (OPT). All washes and incubations prior to the KOH
225 wash were carried out at room temperature (RT) with rocking. Since KOH causes the skeletal preparations
226 to be fragile, the KOH wash and Alizarin red incubation were conducted at RT without rocking.

227
228 Forelimbs stained with Alizarin red and Alcian blue were embedded in 1% agarose (w/v) (MilliporeSigma)
229 hydrogels for optical projection tomography (OPT) imaging (**Figure S2**).^{75,76} To prepare the 1% agarose
230 hydrogels, agarose powder was dissolved into boiling ddH₂O, then sterile filtered using the Steriflip®
231 (MilliporeSigma). The sterilized 1% agarose solution was poured into 35 mm petri dishes and samples were
232 carefully placed into the polymer solutions at medium depth. Embedded samples were allowed to solidify
233 on ice. Excess agarose was removed for all samples, then samples were dehydrated for 24 hr in methanol
234 (Thermo Fisher Scientific). To ensure full dehydration, the methanol solution was replaced 2-3 times during
235 the 24 hr incubation. The following day, samples were cleared for 24 hr using a solution of 50% benzoic
236 acid (v/v) (MilliporeSigma) and 50% benzyl benzoate (v/v) (MilliporeSigma). For OPT imaging, samples
237 were staged using a custom OPT imaging apparatus,⁷⁷ which captures 400 images of each forelimb as it is
238 rotated 360°. Image sets were reconstructed into two-dimensional (2D) sections using NRecon software
239 (Micro Photonics Inc., Allentown, PA, USA), cropped using ImageJ/Fiji software (National Institutes of Health,
240 Bethesda, MD, USA), then segmented using ITK SNAP (Penn Image Computing and Science Laboratory,
241 Philadelphia, PA USA).⁷⁸ Measurements of rudiment lengths, mineral lengths, and joint shape features were
242 quantified from 3D reconstructions using Blender (Blender Foundation, Amsterdam, NL) and 3D Slicer.⁷⁹

243

244 **2.5 Cryohistology and immunofluorescence staining**

245 C57BL/6J embryos harvested at E17.5 were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA, Electron Microscopy
246 Sciences, Hartfield, PA, USA) at 4°C overnight, then transferred to 30% sucrose (w/v) (Thermo Fisher
247 Scientific) in PBS for 24 hr. After sucrose infiltration, embryonic forelimbs were isolated and embedded in
248 optical cutting temperature (OCT) compound (Tissue-Tek, Torrance, CA, USA) for cryosectioning with an
249 EpreDia™ CryoStar™ NX70 Cryostat (Thermo Fisher Scientific). 10 µm thick tissue sections were obtained on
250 cryotape (Section Lab Co, Hiroshima, Japan), as described in detail in a previously published protocol.⁸⁰
251 Tape sections were glued to microscope slides with Norland Optical Adhesive 81 (Norland Products Inc.,
252 Jamesburg, NJ, USA), then processed using standard kits and immunofluorescent protocols. For all protocols,
253 samples were mounted using Fluoromount-GT (Thermo Fisher Scientific), imaged using the ZEISS AxioScan.Z1
254 Slide Scanner (ZEISS, Oberkochen, Germany), and analyzed using ImageJ/Fiji.

255
256 Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) staining was conducted using the Vector blue Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP)
257 substrate kit (SK-5300, Vector Laboratories, Newark, CA, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

258
259 Phalloidin staining with Hoechst counterstain (Thermo Fisher Scientific) was conducted using Alexa Fluor 647
260 Phalloidin (A22287, Thermo Fisher Scientific) according to manufacturer's instructions.

261
262 Immunofluorescent imaging of Collagen 10, Endomucin, Yes-associated protein (YAP), and Connective tissue
263 growth factor-like protein 1 (Cyr61/CCN1) was conducted using standard immunofluorescent protocols.
264 Briefly, glued tissue sections were rehydrated in PBS, then blocked with 5% goat serum (MilliporeSigma) in
265 0.3% Triton-X-100 (MilliporeSigma) for 30 min. The following primary antibodies were applied overnight
266 at 4°C (dilutions and catalog numbers provided): rabbit polyclonal anti-Collagen 10 (ab182563, Abcam,
267 Cambridge, UK), rat monoclonal anti-Endomucin (1:100, sc-65495, Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Dallas, TX,
268 USA), rabbit monoclonal anti-YAP (1:100, 14074, Cell Signaling Technologies, Danvers, MA, USA), rat
269 monoclonal anti-Cyr61 (1:20, MAB4864, R&D Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA). After primary antibody
270 incubation, samples were washed thrice with PBS, then incubated with the following secondary antibodies
271 for 2 hr at RT: goat anti-rat 647 (1:1000, A-21247, Thermo Fisher Scientific), goat anti-rat 488 (1:1000,
272 A-11006, Thermo Fisher Scientific), goat anti-rabbit A647 (1:1000, A-27040, Thermo Fisher Scientific), and
273 goat anti-rabbit A488 (1:1000, A11034, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Hoechst counterstain (1:2000, Thermo
274 Fisher Scientific), was added during the secondary antibody incubation. Samples were then washed thrice
275 with PBS prior to mounting.

276
277 **2.6 Paraffin histology and tinctorial staining**
278 Placentas were isolated during embryo harvests, flash frozen in liquid nitrogen, and stored at -80°C until
279 paraffin histology. Half of each placenta was thawed and processed for paraffin histology using a Thermo
280 Scientific Excelsior AS Tissue Processor (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Processed samples were paraffin-
281 embedded and section to 10 µm using a Leica RM 2030 Microtome (Leica, Bala Cynwyd, PA, USA). Sections
282 were stained for hematoxylin and eosin using standard protocols. Stained sections were imaged using a
283 ZEISS Axio Scan.Z1 Slide Scanner and analyzed using ImageJ/Fiji.

284
285 **2.7 Protein lysis, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), and western blot**
286 The remaining half of each placenta was processed for enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and
287 western blot. Approximately 20 mg of placental tissue was placed in 550 µL of 1X Cell Lysis Buffer (R&D
288 Systems) and homogenized for 5 min at max speed using the Bullet Blender Storm Tissue Homogenizer (Next
289 Advance, Troy, NY, USA). Homogenized lysates were incubated on ice for 15 min, transferred to a clean
290 1.5 mL centrifuge tube, and centrifuged at 13,000 g for 10 min at 4°C using a Sorvall Legend Micro 17R
291 centrifuge (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Protein levels were quantified using a Pierce™ BCA Protein Assay Kit
292 (23227, Thermo Fisher Scientific) according to manufacturer's instructions.

293

294 Placental levels of Insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1) were quantified using the Mouse IGF-1 ELISA Kit
295 (RAB0229, Thermo Fisher Scientific) according to manufacturer's instructions.

296

297 Placental levels of Glucose transporter 1 (GLUT1), Sodium-coupled neutral amino acid transporter 4
298 (SNAT4), and Fatty acid transporter 4 (FATP4) were quantified using standard western blot protocols.
299 Briefly, protein solutions were diluted to 20 µg of protein in 20 µL of RNase-free H₂O (Thermo Fisher
300 Scientific), then mixed in a 1:1 ratio with a solution of 95% 2X Laemmli Buffer (v/v) (Bio-Rad, Philadelphia,
301 PA, USA) and 5% β-mercaptoethanol (v/v) (Bio-Rad). Samples were loaded onto 4-15% Mini-PROTEAN®
302 TGX™ Precast Protein Gels (Bio-Rad) with the Precision Plus Kaleidoscope ladder (Bio-Rad) and run using
303 the Mini-PROTEAN® Tetra System (Bio-Rad). Bands were transferred to Immun-Blot® PVDF Membranes (Bio-
304 Rad) using the Trans Blot® Turbo™ Transfer System (Bio-Rad). Membranes were washed thrice in tris-
305 buffered saline with Tween 20 (TBST, Bio-Rad), then blocked using Blotting-Grade blocker (Bio-Rad) 1.5 hr
306 on a rocker at RT. The following primary antibodies were applied overnight at 4°C with rocking (dilutions
307 and catalog numbers provided): rabbit monoclonal anti-GLUT1 (1:1000, 12939, Cell Signaling
308 Technologies), rabbit polyclonal anti-SLC38A4/SNAT4 (1:1000, 20857-1-AP, Proteintech, Rosemont, IL,
309 USA), rabbit monoclonal anti-SLC27A4/FATP4 (1:1000, ab200353, Abcam), rabbit polyclonal anti-β-actin
310 (1:1000, Cell Signaling Technologies), rabbit polyclonal anti-histone H3 (1:5000, Thermo Fisher Scientific).
311 After primary antibody incubation, samples were washed thrice with TBST, then incubated with anti-rabbit
312 IgG, HRP-linked antibody (1:1000, 7074P2, Cell Signaling Technologies) for 1.5 hr at RT on a rocker. Bands
313 were detected using the Amersham™ ECL™ Prime Western Blotting Detection Reagent (Thermo Fisher
314 Scientific) according to manufacturers instructions, then imaged using the Bio-Rad ChemiDoc™ MP Imaging
315 System (Bio-Rad). Band intensities were quantified using ImageJ/Fiji.

316

317 **2.8 Ex vivo bioreactor culture**

318 Histological images generated by Ahmed et al.⁵⁴ were reanalyzed using quantitative histomorphometry to
319 determine the effects of ex vivo mechanical loading on embryonic limb development. Full materials and
320 methods for generating these samples are provided in Ahmed et al. ⁵⁴ Briefly, E15.5 forelimbs were
321 harvested from WT and Sp^d embryos then cultured using the Ebers TC-3 bioreactor system (Don Whitley
322 Scientific, Bingley, UK). Contralateral limbs were randomly assigned to either Static or Dynamic culture
323 conditions. Static forelimbs were placed within the bioreactor foam supports without any loading. Dynamic
324 forelimb explants were loaded at 0.67 Hz to a displacement of 2 mm for 2 h, 3 times per day. In previous
325 studies, we demonstrated that this compression produces a cyclic flexion angle of approximately 14°, which
326 led to the most physiological growth of tissues.⁴⁹ All explanted limbs were cultured at air-liquid interface
327 with osteogenic media (α-MEM GlutaMAX supplemented with 1% penicillin-streptomycin with amphotericin

328 B, 100 μ M ascorbic acid, 2 mM β -glycerophosphate, and 100 nM dexamethasone) for 7 days at 37°C in
329 normoxic conditions. Media was changed daily.

330

331 Cultured forelimbs were prepared for cryohistology. Full materials and methods for staining and imaging
332 are provided in Ahmed et al.¹⁰ The following antibodies were used (dilutions and catalog numbers provided):
333 mouse monoclonal anti-collagen type II (1:50, MAB8887, MilliporeSigma) and rabbit anti-mouse (Alexa
334 Fluor® 488) (1:200, ab150125, Abcam). Samples were imaged using either the ZEISS LSM 510 (ZEISS) or
335 the Leica CF6 (Leica) confocal laser scanning microscope. Images were analyzed using ImageJ/Fiji.

336

337 **2.9 Statistical analysis and regression**

338 The “pwr2” package in R (Indianapolis, IN, USA) was used to conduct power analysis for large effect sizes
339 ($\alpha = 0.05$, $\beta = 0.20$, $f = 0.4 - 0.6$). GraphPad Prism software Version 10.4.1 (GraphPad Software, San
340 Diego, CA, USA) was used to conduct all statistical analyses. A Student’s t-test was used to determine
341 significant differences for all continuous outcome measurements in the C57BL/6J experiments. Significant
342 differences in litter size were determined using a Chi-squared test. A two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA)
343 with Bonferroni correction was used as a conservative test to determine significant differences for all outcome
344 measurements in the *in vivo* Sp^d experiments. A repeated measures two-way ANOVA with Bonferroni
345 correction was used to determine significant differences for all outcome measurements in the *ex utero* Sp^d
346 experiments.

347

348 Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) with linear regression was performed using R. Individual linear models
349 were generated using predictors of interest for bone length. Significant predictors were input into an
350 exhaustive best-subsets algorithm to determine the best multivariate predictive model of bone length based
351 on Akaike’s information criteria (AIC).⁸¹⁻⁸⁴ In short, optimizing for the lowest AIC selects the model that
352 explains the highest level of variability, while prioritizing models with the fewest predictors. Resultant linear
353 models were graphed using Prism.

354 **3.0 Results**

355 **3.1 Effects of maternal exercise on pregnancy outcomes**

356 We first assessed the effects of maternal exercise on embryonic day 17.5 (E17.5) C57BL/6J mice. Pregnant
357 female dams received daily supervised exercise, one hour per day, starting at E13.5, which coincides with
358 the onset of fetal limb movements and the initiation of endochondral development.^{1,2} Sham controls received
359 equivalent wheel exposure, but their wheels were locked to prevent running (**Figures 1A & S1A**). Pregnant
360 dams were selected between 20 to 24 weeks of age, with no significant differences in maternal age between
361 Sham and Exercise groups (**Figure S1F**). Dams in the Exercise group consistently ran an average of 0.71
362 km/day throughout the exercise period (**Figure S1D**). These exercise conditions did not significantly alter
363 either the mass of the pregnant dams at E17.5 or their litter size (**Figure S1G-H**). Fetuses from these litters
364 were harvested for downstream analyses and the datapoint color in subsequent graphs corresponds to the
365 pregnant dam. For example, a dark red dot would indicate that the fetus came from Exercise Litter #1
366 (**Figure 1**).

367

368 **3.2 Effects of maternal exercise on joint and bone morphogenesis**

369 To assess the effects of maternal exercise on fetal skeletal development, we first assessed morphogenesis
370 of the E17.5 mouse elbow joint using optical projection tomography (OPT) (**Figure 1B-C**). Maternal exercise
371 increased humeral medial condyle width, height, and depth (**Figure 1D-F**), lateral condyle width, height, and
372 depth (**Figure 1G-I**).

373

374 To assess the effects of maternal exercise on bone development, we performed optical projection
375 tomography (OPT) and microcomputed tomography (μ CT) imaging (**Figure 2A&G**). Maternal exercise
376 significantly increased humerus rudiment length and mineralized length of the bony primary ossification
377 center, but did not affect the mineralization ratio (*i.e.*, the ratio of mineralized length to rudiment length)
378 (**Figure 2B-D**). This indicates that maternal exercise proportionally stimulated rudiment growth and
379 mineralization. The development of the deltoid tuberosity has been shown to be particularly sensitive to
380 absent muscle stimulation.⁴⁴ Maternal exercise significantly increased deltoid tuberosity volume (**Figure 2E**),
381 even after normalization by the rudiment length (**Figure 2F**). Using μ CT, we confirmed that maternal exercise
382 increased humeral bone volume and bone length (**Figure 2G-I**), and further showed that maternal exercise
383 significantly increased bone tissue mineral density (TMD) (**Figure 2J**).

384

385 **3.3 Effects of maternal exercise on placental transport**

386 Maternal exercise may regulate fetal development by altering the transport of factors or nutrients across
387 the placenta. Maternal exercise significantly increased fetal weight, suggesting that maternal exercise may
388 affect overall fetal development (**Figure 3A**). Based on this finding, we performed an analysis of covariance
389 (ANCOVA) to control for the contributions of fetal weight change to maternal exercise-induced variation in

390 fetal bone length. If bone length is best predicted by separate regression lines for each exercise condition,
391 this would indicate that there is an effect of exercise on bone length that cannot be explained by fetal
392 weight. In contrast, a best-fit by a single regression line for both exercise conditions would indicate that
393 variation in bone length can be explained by changes in fetal weight. We found that separate regression
394 lines for each exercise condition best predicted bone length, with a persistently significant effect of maternal
395 exercise after controlling for variation in fetal weight ($p < 0.001$, **Figures 3B and S3**). Thus, the increase in
396 bone length induced by maternal exercise cannot be fully explained by differences in fetal weight.

397
398 We next evaluated hierarchical measures of placental. The fetal weight to placental weight (FW:PW) ratio
399 reflects the capacity of the placenta to support a fetus of a given weight, and can be altered by changes
400 in fetal weight, placental weight, or both.^{85,86} Maternal exercise was associated with significantly increased
401 fetal weight and decreased placental weight, resulting in a significantly increased FW:PW ratio (**Figure**
402 **3A,C-D**). To more directly measure placental transport capacity, we measured the area ratio between the
403 labyrinth zone (LZ) and junctional zone (JZ) of the placenta. The higher the value of the LZ:JZ ratio, the
404 greater the assumed placental transport efficiency.^{85,86} Maternal exercise did not significantly alter the LZ:JZ
405 ratio (**Figure 3E-F**). Finally, we evaluated the expression of proteins known to regulate fetal growth through
406 regulation of placental transport. Insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1) is a major upstream regulator of
407 placental nutrient transporter expression and IGF-1 levels are strongly correlated with fetal growth
408 outcomes.^{70,87} Maternal exercise did not significantly alter placental levels of IGF-1, but significantly
409 decreased the concentration of IGF-1 in fetal plasma, which was pooled for all fetuses within a litter (**Figure**
410 **3G-H**). To ensure that similar placental IGF-1 levels were consistent with similar placental nutrient transport,
411 we measured the expression of the major nutrient transporters involved in placental-fetal glucose, amino
412 acid, and fatty acid transport: glucose transporter 1 (GLUT1), sodium-coupled neutral amino acid transporter
413 4 (SNAT4), and fatty acid transporter 4 (FATP4), respectively.⁷⁰ Consistent with our LZ:JZ and placental IGF-
414 1 findings, maternal exercise did not alter placental levels of GLUT1, SNAT4, or FATP4 (**Figure 5E-H**).
415 Together, these findings do not constitute compelling evidence for a critical role of altered placental transport
416 in maternal exercise-induced fetal skeletal development; however, they do not preclude the potential
417 contributions of transplacental humoral factors.

418 419 **3.4 Mechanoregulation of endochondral ossification via maternal exercise**

420 Beyond placental transport, maternal exercise may also stimulate skeletal development through passive
421 movement-induced mechanical stimulation. Based on our prior studies on the mechanotransductive roles of
422 the transcriptional regulators Yes-associated protein (YAP) and Transcriptional co-activator with PDZ-binding
423 motif (TAZ) in skeletal development,^{53,81,88,89} we evaluated YAP/TAZ expression and the abundance of the
424 canonical YAP target gene, Cysteine-rich angiogenic inducer 61 (Cyr61), in the developing bone. YAP is
425 transcriptionally active in the nucleus, and its cytoplasmic-nuclear transport can be induced by a variety of

426 signals, including mechanical cues and morphogen signaling.⁸⁹ We observed robust YAP expression in the
427 developing skeleton, including in the bone collar (BC) and the primary ossification center (POC) of both
428 groups (**Figure 4A**). We found that maternal exercise significantly increased Cyr61 abundance in the bone
429 collar (**Figure 4B**). The increase in Cyr61 abundance in the primary ossification center was not statistically
430 significant ($p = 0.058$) (**Figure 4C**).

431
432 Next, we evaluated the effects of maternal exercise on growth plate morphometry, alkaline phosphatase
433 (ALP) activity, and neovascular morphometry in the developing humerus. These analyses were prioritized
434 based on our findings that osteoprogenitor cell YAP/TAZ signaling regulates fetal bone development by
435 coupling osteoprogenitor mobilization to blood vessel invasion for chondro-osseous junction remodeling and
436 bone formation.⁵³ Maternal exercise significantly reduced hypertrophic zone length (**Figure 5A-B**), consistent
437 with increased chondro-osseous junction remodeling.⁵³ Maternal exercise did not alter ALP activity, which
438 marks osteogenic cell activity, in either the endochondral primary ossification center or the intramembranous
439 bone collar (**Figure 5C-E**). Maternal exercise did not significantly alter medullary vessel area or density
440 (**Figure 5F-H**), but significantly increased bone collar vessel area and density (**Figure 5I-J**). Maternal exercise
441 also significantly increased vessel area and density in the metaphyseal region, which captures the looping
442 vessels along the chondro-osseous junction (**Figure 5K-L**). Together, these data suggest that maternal exercise
443 enhanced growth plate remodeling and neovascularization, but did not directly stimulate osteogenesis, per
444 se.

445 446 **3.5 Effects of maternal exercise on fetal akinesia-impaired limb development**

447 We next tested whether maternal exercise would influence joint and bone formation in the Splotch-delayed
448 (Sp^d) model of fetal akinesia.³ The Sp^d homozygous fetus exhibits limited muscle development and lacks
449 spontaneous limb movements;³²⁻³⁴ thus, this model has intact maternofetal transport, but dramatically altered
450 mechanical loading in the limbs. In these experiments, female dams pregnant with wild-type and Sp^d embryos
451 were exercised from E13.5 to E15.5, inclusive, with harvest at E16.5. Like previous experiments, dams in the
452 Sham group had access to locked wheels to prevent running.

453
454 Maternal exercise stimulated elbow joint morphogenesis in both wild-type and Sp^d fetuses, rescuing fetal
455 akinesia-impaired joint parameters (**Figure 6A-B**). Specifically, fetal akinesia significantly reduced humeral
456 medial condyle width and height (**Figure 6C-D**) and lateral condyle width and height (**Figure 6F-G**), but
457 these defects were rescued in Sp^d embryos exposed to maternal exercise. Medial and lateral condyle depth
458 were not significantly reduced by fetal akinesia, but were significantly increased by maternal exercise in
459 Sp^d fetuses (**Figure 6E&H**).

460

461 Fetal akinesia significantly reduced humerus rudiment length, mineralized length, and mineralization ratio,
462 but these defects were also rescued by maternal exercise (**Figure 7A-D**). Similar to joint morphogenesis,
463 maternal exercise rescued these key bone development outcomes. Lastly, we measured the effects of fetal
464 akinesia and maternal exercise on morphogenesis of the deltoid tuberosity. Previous studies showed that the
465 cartilaginous rudiment of the deltoid tuberosity forms in Sp^d mice at E14.5, but resorbs by E18.5 due to the
466 absence of stimulatory mechanical cues.⁴⁴ Consistently, we observed significantly reduced deltoid tuberosity
467 volume in Sp^d fetuses at E16.5 (**Figure 7E**). However, maternal exercise rescued deltoid tuberosity volume
468 to the level of wild-type fetuses. Importantly, the maternal exercise-induced rescue of deltoid tuberosity
469 morphogenesis was preserved after controlling for overall rudiment growth (*i.e.*, after normalizing by
470 rudiment length) (**Figure 7F**).

471
472 Finally, we used mechanostimulation bioreactor culture of explanted embryonic limbs to test the effects of
473 mechanical loading on joint morphogenesis, in the absence of systemic maternal factors, by using *ex utero*
474 mechanical stimulation bioreactor culture. Briefly, E15.5 embryonic forelimbs from wild-type and Sp^d fetuses
475 were explanted and cultured for 7 days in a dynamic loading bioreactor. The implemented dynamic loading
476 protocol was previously optimized by our group to promote proper limb morphogenesis *in vitro*.^{49,50}
477 Contralateral static control limbs from each genotype were cultured in the bioreactor without cyclic loading
478 (**Figure 8A**). Under static conditions, wild-type and Sp^d joints were not significantly different in condyle
479 height or condyle area (**Figure 8B-D**). This suggests that unloaded WT limbs exhibited similarly impaired
480 joint morphogenesis as Sp^d limbs due to explantation-induced arrest of active movement. However, dynamic
481 loading significantly increased condyle height and condyle area, in both wild-type and Sp^d limbs. Together,
482 these data demonstrate that morphogenesis of both WT and Sp^d limbs are responsive to mechanical stimuli.
483

484 **4.0 Discussion**

485 Here, we describe the effects of maternal wheel running exercise on fetal skeletal development in mice. In
486 wild-type fetuses, maternal exercise stimulated joint morphogenesis, bone growth, deltoid tuberosity
487 formation, chondro-osseous junction remodeling, and blood vessel invasion. These changes could not be fully
488 explained by altered placental transport; however, our data strongly support a role of mechanical
489 stimulation by maternal exercise in fetal limb development. Using the Sp^d mouse model of fetal akinesia,
490 which features normal maternofetal communication but lacks fetal movement, we found that maternal
491 exercise rescued fetal akinesia-impaired joint morphogenesis, bone growth, and deltoid tuberosity
492 formation. Further, application of passive limb movement in explanted limbs, removed from maternal
493 systemic factors, similarly stimulated joint morphogenesis. Taken together, our data suggest that maternal
494 exercise promotes fetal skeletal development, likely via both systemic maternofetal communication and
495 physical stimulation of the developing limbs. These findings demonstrate that maternal exercise regulates
496 fetal skeletal development, implicate maternal exercise as a platform for studying developmental
497 mechanobiology of the skeleton *in vivo*, and motivate continued study into maternal exercise as a potential
498 *in utero* intervention for fetal hypokinesia.

499
500 Maternal exercise can benefit offspring development. Controlled trials in humans showed that moderate
501 maternal exercise (40-60% of maximum oxygen consumption (VO₂ max), up to 50 min/day, 3 days/week)
502 significantly increased fetal cardiac function at 36 weeks gestation⁹⁰ and increased offspring brain maturity
503 at 15 days old.⁹¹ Corroborating enhanced cognitive function outcomes, a preclinical rat study found that
504 moderate-intensity maternal treadmill exercise (up to 8 m/min, 30 min/day, 5 days/week) significantly
505 increased spatial learning memory in offspring.⁹² Preclinical models have also demonstrated the benefits of
506 maternal exercise on offspring liver function. Specifically, moderate-intensity maternal treadmill exercise
507 (up to 21 m/min, up to 60 min/day, 6 days/week) protected rat offspring from liver dysfunction associated
508 with maternal high-fat/high-sugar diet⁹³ and voluntary maternal wheel running exercise protected mouse
509 offspring from developing non-alcoholic fatty liver disease associated with maternal high-fat diet.⁹⁴
510 Voluntary maternal wheel running exercise in mice also protect offspring from developing mammary tumors
511 after carcinogen challenge.⁹⁵ Some studies have also described that maternal exercise prior to conception
512 may benefit pregnancy and offspring.⁹⁶ In our study, all mice, including sham and exercise groups, received
513 the same *ad libitum* wheel acclimation prior to pregnancy. We used a targeted exercise approach, in which
514 we exposed pregnant dams to one hour of supervised wheel running each day (broken in four 15-min bouts),
515 for up to four days during the key window of fetal joint and bone development. We selected this limited
516 regimen to mimic an achievable exercise program and because we observed that pregnant dams
517 progressively diminish their running distances as pregnancy progresses when provided wheels *ad libitum*.
518 Our findings contribute to a growing body of maternal exercise literature and pose new questions about
519 how maternal exercise affects orthopaedic tissues.

520

521 We do not yet understand how maternal exercise affects offspring skeletal development. To date, only
522 three preclinical studies have measured effects of maternal exercise on offspring skeletal development, but
523 all focused on postnatal skeletal outcomes. One study found that voluntary wheel running exercise by
524 pregnant mice, throughout gestation, increased osteogenic gene expression in the offspring femora,
525 measured at two-months old.⁹⁷ Conversely, another study found that subjecting pregnant rats to regular
526 squat exercise throughout pregnancy (*i.e.*, food and water were raised so pregnant rats needed to stand
527 on fully extended hindlimbs to eat and drink) significantly reduced tibial bone mineral density in the
528 offspring, measured at four months old.⁹⁸ The final study found that mild maternal treadmill exercise (30%
529 VO₂ max, unspecified exercise frequency) did not significantly alter femur length or bone mineral content in
530 rat offspring at three-months old.⁹⁹ In synthesis, these findings suggest that intensity and frequency of
531 maternal exercise can regulate offspring skeletal health: too little exercise may not provide adequate stimuli,
532 but too much may be detrimental. A recent systematic review and meta-analysis reported no significant
533 difference in birthweight of babies born from mothers who completed vigorous intensity exercise in the third
534 trimester compared with controls, but observed a small but significant increase in gestational age at delivery
535 and a decrease in risk of prematurity.¹⁰⁰ Our findings, using preclinical mouse models, suggest that moderate
536 exercise during late gestation stimulates fetal skeletal development, but further studies are required to assay
537 long-term benefits.

538

539 Synthesizing our findings, we posit that maternal exercise promotes fetal skeletal development, in part
540 through passive physical stimulation of the fetal limb. We observed effects of maternal exercise on
541 YAP/TAZ-target gene expression, growth plate remodeling, and vascular morphogenesis at the chondro-
542 osseous junction, which are consistent with our prior findings that YAP and TAZ mediate mechanical control
543 of limb development and regulate neovascular invasion-mediated growth plate remodeling.⁵³ However, it
544 is important to note that YAP/TAZ activity *per se*, particularly *in vivo*, is not a univariate indicator of
545 mechanotransduction. Further work will be needed to test for a mechanistic role of YAP/TAZ
546 mechanotransduction in maternal exercise-induced limb morphogenesis. Second, maternal exercise
547 substantially rescued joint and bone morphogenesis in the Sp^d model of fetal akinesia, which disrupts fetal
548 movement without altering maternofetal communication. Notably, maternal exercise prevented akinesia-
549 induced resorption of the deltoid tuberosity, an established hallmark of mechanoregulated
550 morphogenesis.^{35,57} Normalizing deltoid tuberosity volume by rudiment length, to control for overall rudiment
551 growth induced by maternal exercise, did not abrogate the rescue, further suggesting a local mechanical
552 response. Lastly, we used an orthogonal *ex utero* approach for mechanical stimulation of explanted limbs,
553 removed from systemic factors.^{49-51,53,54} These data show that mechanical cues are sufficient to stimulate joint
554 morphogenesis in both wild-type and Sp^d mice.

555

556 In addition to mechanical stimulation, our data support a contribution of maternal-derived signals on fetal
557 skeletal development. Maternal exercise increased fetal weight and FW:PW ratio, an approximate measure
558 of placental transport efficiency, but we found no significant changes in more direct measurements of
559 placental transport capacity (i.e., LZ/JZ ratio, nutrient transporter expression). These findings are consistent
560 with previous studies that found FW:PW ratio changes without significantly altered downstream
561 measurements of placental transport.^{101,102} A previous study in rats found that moderate maternal treadmill
562 exercise (up to 17 m/min, up to 50 min/day, 7 days/week) increased fetal weight and placental transport
563 efficiency via increased IGF signaling.⁶⁷ In addition, dysregulation of the IGF system has been implicated in
564 the pathogenesis of fetal growth restriction in mice,¹⁰³⁻¹⁰⁵ rats,^{106,107} rabbits,¹⁰⁸ sheep,¹⁰⁹⁻¹¹¹ and
565 humans.^{112,113} However, we did not observe changes in placental zone morphometry,^{85,86} placental IGF-1
566 levels,^{70,87} or nutrient transporter expression.^{85,86} Compared to these prior studies, our experimental design
567 featured different intensity, modality (i.e., wheel running vs. treadmill) and duration (i.e., 3-4 days vs. 20
568 days). Although we do not observe evidence of increased IGF signaling in our exercise model, it is possible
569 that other maternally secreted humoral signals are involved. For example, a mouse study found that
570 moderate maternal treadmill exercise (up to 40-65% VO₂, up to 60 min/day, 7 days/week) enhanced fetal
571 muscle development via elevated apelin signaling, which demethylated the promoter region of *Ppargc1a*
572 and promoted mitochondriogenesis.⁶⁸ Future studies will be required to determine these additional putative
573 contributions.

574
575 This study has limitations. First, our study did not vary exercise duration or intensity. Human pregnancy
576 guidelines recommend that maternal exercise can be beneficial through means that depend on the intensity,
577 duration, and exercise modality.⁶² Although the mice in our study ran consistent distances, our supervised
578 wheel running approach could not modulate exercise intensity. Future studies using controlled treadmill
579 running and longitudinal endpoint assessments of maternal exercise physiology will be required. Second, we
580 utilize the *Sp^d* mouse model of fetal akinesia, which produces fetuses that lack mature skeletal muscle. Though
581 this mouse represents an extreme case of absent fetal movements, the *Sp^d* model prevented us from studying
582 possible influences of trophic factors from fetal muscle in the response to maternal exercise. In future studies,
583 we aim to use the *mdg/mdg* mouse as a more clinically relevant model of amyoplasia that may preserve
584 bone-muscle crosstalk. Lastly, though our evidence suggests that maternal exercise regulates fetal skeletal
585 development in part through passive restoration of mechanical signals, our data also support contributions
586 of altered maternofetal communication. This study was not designed to define the underlying
587 mechanotransductive mechanisms and further research will be necessary to identify putative humoral signals
588 that may mediate maternofetal crosstalk. Likewise, we do not yet know whether the developing cell
589 populations affected by fetal akinesia are directly stimulated by maternal exercise, or whether the observed
590 rescue effects are mediated by indirect cellular mechanisms.

591

592 Taken together, these findings identify maternal exercise as a regulator of fetal skeletal development,
593 providing a platform for studying skeletal developmental mechanobiology and suggesting potential
594 therapeutic applications for fetuses with impaired movement.

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883 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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886 All data needed to evaluate the conclusions in the paper are present in the paper and/or the

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890 The graphical abstract and schematics in Figures 1, 8, and S1 were generated using BioRender.com.

891 **7.0 Figure Legends**

892

893 **Figure 1. Maternal exercise stimulates fetal joint morphogenesis.** (A) Schematic representation of Sham
894 and Exercise pregnant dams. (B) Optical projection tomography (OPT) reconstructions of alizarin red and
895 alcian blue-stained forelimbs at E17.5. Cartilaginous regions of the scapula, humerus, radius, and ulna are
896 marked in green, purple, orange, and yellow, respectively. Ossified regions are marked in gray. Scale bar
897 = 1 mm. (C) Zoomed projections of the cartilaginous distal humerus. The width, depth, and height of the
898 lateral condyle and medial condyle are marked in the frontal, sagittal, and coronal planes. Scale bar =
899 500 μm . (D) Medial condyle width, (E) medial condyle height, (F) medial condyle depth, (G) lateral condyle
900 width, (H) lateral condyle height, and (I) lateral condyle depth. Fetuses from the same litter are marked by
901 the same color datapoint. * = $p < 0.05$ using a Student's t-test.
902

903 **Figure 2. Maternal exercise stimulates fetal bone development.** (A) Optical projection tomography (OPT)
904 reconstructions of embryonic day 17.5 (E17.5) humeri. The rudiment length and mineralized length are
905 marked with white arrows. The deltoid tuberosity is contoured in black. Scale bar = 500 μm . (B) Rudiment
906 length, (C) mineralized length, and (D) mineralized ratio (i.e., the ratio of mineralized length to rudiment
907 length). (E) Deltoid tuberosity volume and (F) deltoid tuberosity volume normalized by rudiment length. (G)
908 Three-dimensional microcomputed tomography (μCT) reconstructions of the E17.5 humeri. Scale bar = 500
909 μm . (H) Bone volume, (I) bone length, and (J) tissue mineral density (TMD). Fetuses from the same litter are
910 marked by the same color datapoint. * = $p < 0.05$ using a Student's t-test.
911

912 **Figure 3. Placental transport cannot fully explain how maternal exercise regulates limb development.**
913 (A) Fetal weight (FW). (B) Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) for effect of maternal exercise on humerus
914 bone length, accounting for variation in fetal weight. Bands indicate 95% confidence interval for each curve.
915 Goodness of fit (R^2) and linear equation are reported for each linear regression. (C) Placental weight (PW),
916 and (D) FW:PW ratio. (E) Hematoxylin and eosin micrographs of embryonic day 17.5 (E17.5) placentas.
917 Scale bar = 1 mm. (F) Labyrinth zone (LZ) area to junctional zone (JZ) area ratio (LZ:JZ). (G) Placental levels
918 of insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1) and (H) fetal plasma levels of IGF-1, pooled by litter. (I) Western
919 blots for glucose transporter 1 (GLUT1, molecular weight (MW) = 54 kDa), sodium-coupled neutral amino
920 acid transporter 4 (SNAT4, MW = 60 kDa), and fatty acid transporter 4 (FATP4, MW = 72 kDa). Histone
921 H3 (MW = 15 kDa) and β -actin (MW = 42 kDa) were used as loading controls. (J) Relative GLUT1 intensity,
922 (K) relative SNAT4 intensity, and (L) relative FATP4 intensity. Fetuses from the same litter are marked by
923 the same color datapoint. * = $p < 0.05$ using a Student's t-test.
924

925 **Figure 4. Maternal exercise upregulates YAP signaling in fetal bone.** (A) Fluorescent staining for nuclei
926 (DAPI), Yes-associated protein (YAP), and Cysteine-rich angiogenic inducer 61 (Cyr61) in embryonic day
927 17.5 (E17.5) humeri. Scale bar = 250 μm . (B) Bone collar (BC) Cyr61-positive area, and (C) primary
928 ossification center (POC) Cyr61-positive area. Fetuses from the same litter are marked by the same color
929 datapoint. * = $p < 0.05$ using a Student's t-test.
930

931 **Figure 5. Maternal exercise alters growth plate morphometry and bone neovascularization.** (A)
932 Fluorescent staining for collagen type 10 alpha 1 chain (Col10a1) in the proximal hypertrophic zone (HZ)
933 of embryonic day 17.5 (E17.5) humeri. Scale bar = 500 μm . (B) HZ length. (C) Fluorescent staining for
934 alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity in E17.5 humeri. Scale bar = 250 μm . (D) Bone collar (BC) ALP activity
935 and (E) primary ossification center (POC) ALP activity. (F) Fluorescent staining for blood vessels (endomucin)
936 in E17.5 humeri. Scale bar = 250 μm . (G) BC vessel area, (H) BC vessel density, (I) medullary vessel area,
937 (J) medullary vessel density, (K) metaphyseal vessel area, and (L) metaphyseal vessel density. Fetuses from
938 the same litter are marked by the same color datapoint. * = $p < 0.05$ using a Student's t-test.
939

940 **Figure 6. Maternal exercise rescues fetal akinesia-impaired joint morphogenesis.** (A) Optical projection
941 tomography (OPT) reconstructions of embryonic day 16.5 (E16.5) forelimbs in wild-type (WT) and Splotch-

942 delayed (Sp^d) mice. Cartilaginous regions of the scapula, humerus, radius, and ulna are marked in green,
943 purple, orange, and yellow, respectively. Ossified regions are marked in gray. **(B)** Zoomed projections of
944 the cartilaginous distal humerus. **(C)** Medial condyle width, **(D)** medial condyle height, **(E)** medial condyle
945 depth, **(F)** lateral condyle width, **(G)** lateral condyle height, and **(H)** lateral condyle depth. Fetuses from the
946 same litter are marked by the same color datapoint. * = $p < 0.05$ using a two-way ANOVA with Bonferroni
947 correction.

948
949 **Figure 7. Maternal exercise rescues fetal akinesia-impaired bone development.** **(A)** Optical projection
950 tomography (OPT) reconstructions of embryonic day 16.5 (E16.5) humeri in wild-type (WT) and Splotch-
951 delayed (Sp^d) mice. The rudiment length and mineralized length are marked with white arrows. The deltoid
952 tuberosity is contoured in black. Scale bar = 500 μm . **(B)** Rudiment length, **(C)** mineralized length, **(D)**
953 mineralization ratio, **(E)** deltoid tuberosity volume, and **(F)** rudiment length-normalized deltoid tuberosity
954 volume. Fetuses from the same litter are marked by the same color datapoint. * = $p < 0.05$ using a two-way
955 ANOVA with Bonferroni correction.
956

957 **Figure 8. Mechanical loading, in the absence of systemic maternal factors, rescues joint morphogenesis**
958 **impaired by lack of movement.** **(A)** Schematic representation of ex utero mechanostimulation bioreactor
959 culture of embryonic forelimbs from wild-type (WT) and Splotch-delayed (Sp^d) mice. **(B)** Fluorescent staining
960 for collagen type 2 alpha 1 chain (Col2a1) in the proximal joint of ex utero forelimbs. Scale bar = 200 μm .
961 **(C)** Condyle height and **(D)** condyle area. Limbs from the same fetus are marked by the same shape and
962 connecting line. * = $p < 0.05$ using a two-way ANOVA with Bonferroni correction.

Supplemental Figure 1. Wheel acclimation and maternal exercise regimen. (A) Schematic representation of maternal exercise modalities. Female mice were acclimated to running wheels with *ad libitum* access for two weeks prior to timed pregnancies. After timed pregnancies, pregnant dams had no wheel access until embryonic day 13.5 (E13.5). At E13.5, pregnant dams were assigned to one of two exercise modalities: (1) *Ad libitum* wheel access until harvest at E17.5 or (2) Supervised wheel running daily until harvest at E17.5. Each exercise modality included Sham mice, which had the same wheel exposure, but wheels were locked so that the pregnant dams could not use them to exercise. Embryos were harvested at E17.5 for downstream analyses. (B) Daily running distance throughout the two-week acclimation period. (C) Daily running distance for pregnant dams using the *Ad libitum* exercise modality. (D) Daily running distance for pregnant dams using the Supervised running exercise modality. Each line represents one pregnant dam. (E) Schematic and legend for pregnant C57BL/6J dams used in this study. Each pregnant dam is noted by a different shade of blue for Sham animals and red for Exercise animals. (F) Maternal age, (G) maternal mass at E17.5, and (H) litter size.

Supplemental Figure 2. Optical projection tomography (OPT) imaging of fetal forelimbs. (A) OPT apparatus with high-resolution camera, rotating stage, and magnetic sample holder marked by yellow arrows. (B) Example process for how a series of 400 brightfield images captured at 360° was reconstructed and converted into a 3D model.

Supplemental Figure 3. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) for effect of maternal exercise on humerus bone length, accounting for variation in fetal weight. (A) Single linear regression fitting humerus length vs. fetal weight for Sham and Exercise fetuses. (B) Separate linear regressions fitting humerus length vs. fetal weight for Sham and Exercise fetuses. Bands indicate 95% confidence interval for each curve. Goodness of fit (R^2) and linear equation are reported for each linear regression.